

Published Financial Statement as a Correlate of Investment Decision among Commercial Bank Stakeholders in Nigeria

Authors : C. F. Popoola, K. Akinsanya, S. B. Babarinde, D. A. Farinde

Abstract : This study investigated published financial statement as correlate of investment decision among commercial bank stakeholders in Nigeria. A correlation research design was used in the study. 180 users of published financial statement were purposively sampled from Lagos and Ibadan. Data generated were analyzed using Pearson correlation and regression. The findings of the study revealed that, balance sheet is negatively related with investment decision ($r = -.483$; $p < .01$) while income statement ($r = .249$; $p < .001$), notes on the account ($r = .230$; $p < .001$), cash flow statement ($r = .202$; $p < .001$), value added statement ($r = .328$; $p < .001$) and five-year financial summary ($r = .191$; $p < .01$) are positively related with investment decision. Findings also revealed that components of published financial statement significantly predicted good investment decision ($R^2 = .983$; $F(5,175) = 284.5$; $p < .05$) for commercial bank stakeholders. Therefore, it was suggested that Nigeria banks and professional bodies should instigate programs that will increase the knowledge of stakeholders on published financial statement.

Keywords : commercial banks, financial statement, income statement, investment decision, stakeholders

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